

Machine learning-driven cellular–satellite multi-connectivity for monitoring livestock transport in rural areas[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Emerging domains such as wireless industrial control, vehicular communications, smart grids, and augmented reality demand low latency, high throughput, and high reliability from wireless communication systems. Unfortunately, single connectivity (SC) communications frequently fail to fulfill these stringent requirements. To address these challenges, employing a multi-connectivity (MC) solution appears to be a promising technique. In this paper, in the context of Horizon Europe COMECT project, we seek to develop a multi-connectivity solution that intelligently integrates cellular and satellite networks for the purpose of monitoring livestock transport in rural regions where 5G coverage is limited. Multi-connectivity can be helpful for meeting EU regulations requiring seamless communication between transport units and the operational center to ensure animal welfare during transit. To achieve this, we employ machine learning (ML) models within a Classification and Regression framework in the proposed multi-connectivity solution. The ML models process radio-related key performance indicators (KPIs) as inputs to estimate network throughput and latency. The outputs of the model are used to decide whether to continue with the cellular link or activate the backup satellite link in the multi-connectivity setup, ensuring an almost uninterrupted connection. This capability is particularly crucial in regions where 5G coverage is limited, and maintaining a reliable connection is essential. To evaluate the proposed framework, we used a hybrid emulation setup based on experimental data collected in the northern part of Denmark. The emulation results demonstrate that the MC solution significantly outperforms the cellular SC. Although our solution is designed for livestock transport monitoring, it can be adapted for other applications, such as precision farming, in areas with insufficient 5G availability.

1. Introduction

The increasing popularity of online gaming, virtual reality (VR), and live video streaming have resulted in a growing need for connectivity solutions with low latency and high throughput [1,2]. However, conventional connectivity solutions often struggle to adapt dynamically to fluctuating network conditions [3]. In traditional connectivity, devices typically connect to a network through a single connection, such as Wi-Fi or cellular network, or rely on a single network interface. This configuration makes the system vulnerable to failure or performance degradation if the connection experiences any issues [4]. Furthermore, packet is managed using predetermined rules and routes that are not adjusted to changing conditions. For instance, the load balancing scheme distributes traffic using static algorithms that overlook real-time network performance, allocating resources such as bandwidth and processing power based on fixed configurations [5]. This can result

in inefficient resource use either through over-provisioning (wasting resources) or under-provisioning (causing performance issues). Further, connection issues are generally addressed reactively rather than proactively. Reliance on static, fixed configurations in traditional connectivity solutions often results in delays, leading to noticeable drops in performance [6], and lack the ability to adapt dynamically to changing network conditions, which is crucial for real-time optimization and adaptability [7].

In this context, *multi-connectivity* can be seen as a promising solution, as it allows the simultaneous utilization of multiple network connections, thus improving overall network reliability, quality of experience (QoE), and ensuring uninterrupted connectivity even if one connection experiences problems [8]. In multi-connectivity, these networks can be terrestrial networks (e.g., cellular, Wi-Fi, Ethernet), non-terrestrial networks (e.g., LEO/GEO satellite, drone-based communication), or a combination of both. Generally, terrestrial networks (TN)

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Fig. 1. Multi-connectivity with cellular and satellite networks.

tend to be more affordable than non-terrestrial networks (NTN), particularly when it comes to satellite communication [9]. However, satellite communication has the advantage of providing extensive coverage and can offer services in remote locations where cellular communication has limited or no coverage [10]. Recent developments toward 6G and the proliferation of IoT devices have further emphasized the need for robust, flexible, and ubiquitous connectivity. In this regard, NTN technologies, such as satellite constellations are increasingly being considered for integration into future network standards. Our work aligns with these trends by proposing an emulation-based multi-connectivity framework that can support the seamless integration of TN and NTN, offering a practical step forward in the direction envisioned by ongoing 3GPP [11] and IMT-2030 discussions [12].

In our previous work [13], we introduced a machine learning (ML)-based classification framework to intelligently activate multi-connectivity by integrating 5G and satellite networks. This approach was designed to support the monitoring of livestock transport in rural regions with limited 5G coverage, i.e., the use case illustrated in Fig. 1. Livestock transport is one of the scenarios explored within the Horizon Europe COMMECT project which aims to bridge the digital divide in rural areas through cost-effective and environmentally sustainable connectivity solutions. By leveraging real-time network conditions, the ML classifier dynamically selects the most appropriate link, ensuring continuous and reliable connectivity throughout the entire route. The solution effectively addressed the throughput requirements for this use case. In this paper, we consider both throughput and latency requirements for the target use-case. In addition, we incorporate a regression framework along with the previously studied classification framework. By considering both the latency and throughput requirements, we cover a more complete spectrum regarding QoE/Quality of Service (QoS) from the end-user perspective. In the COMMECT project use-case, every 15 min, data regarding location and sensors must be sent to the transport center in uplink. Given an estimated packet size of 5 KB, an uplink throughput of 16 Kbps is sufficient for meeting both current and future data requirements. For the downlink, the system should support applications that determine optimal routes based on traffic conditions, animal disease control zones, and weather forecasts. This requires downloading up to 5 MB of content within 3–5 s, which necessitates a downlink throughput of 8–15 Mbps [14]. To guarantee uninterrupted service and reliable connectivity for seamless livestock transport applications, the system must ensure 99.9% uptime. The main challenge lies in maintaining network stability, as single-connectivity conditions often fail to support the required uptime throughout the entire route. Additionally, maintaining a low latency is essential to guarantee a good user experience in livestock transportation systems or other applications involving real-time tracking or navigation. Though the acceptable latency may differ based on specific application requirements and user expectations, a recommended guideline for interactive applications like Google Maps aims for a latency of less than 100 ms. This threshold ensures that the application remains responsive and delivers a seamless user experience. The study in [15] highlights various applications demanding latency of less than 100 ms, for example,

real-time medical monitoring (< 100 ms) and gaming or interactive services (< 10 ms). Similarly, the 3GPP TS22.261 specification defines the comparable latency requirements for industrial scenarios [16].

The COMMECT project outlines two strategies to manage packet flow: (1) smart packet duplication and (2) dynamic routing (or packet switching), aimed at optimizing performance under mobile conditions. In multi-connectivity scenarios, smart packet duplication refers to a technique where, if a network link cannot meet the application requirements, the system duplicates the packet and sends it over both the primary and alternate links. Smart packet duplication is beneficial when the primary objectives are minimizing latency and maximizing reliability at the expense of increased resource utilization. When properly configured, a smart packet duplication approach can effectively reduce packet loss. However, this may lead to increased network traffic, energy use, and cost if both connections are utilized concurrently for extended periods. To minimize bandwidth usage, energy, and cost, a dynamic routing scheme can prove beneficial in multi-connectivity scenarios. This method involves utilizing a smart scheduler or router to dynamically redirect packet flows between different network links based on specific policies or the current state of networks. Such a method could be particularly beneficial in mobile settings, as it has the capability to minimize unnecessary data transmission and adjust to varying network conditions. By conserving bandwidth and potentially extending battery life, dynamic routing shows promise as a sustainable and efficient alternative to continuous packet duplications. In this study, we adapted the dynamic routing scheme in the multi-connectivity solution.

The main contributions of this paper are threefold:

- A dynamic routing scheme, based on an ML model with both classification and regression, that proactively predicts activation of satellite connectivity from measured radio key performance indicators (KPIs).
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of the dynamic routing scheme in terms of network KPIs, under network conditions that replicate real-world measurements.
- A hybrid emulation framework that combines the OpenSand satellite link emulator [17] with Traffic Control Network Emulator (tc-netem) [18] for cellular link emulation, and an own-developed multi-connectivity tool [19] for dynamic transport layer routing.

Our goal is to develop a generalizable solution that does not rely on location-specific tuning, but instead leverages radio KPIs to predict network KPIs for switching between available links. This approach allows the solution to remain adaptable across various scenarios without being constrained by specific geographical conditions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses the related work. Section 3 provides an overview of the measurement campaign and parameter analysis, explaining the preprocessing of the measurements before feeding them to the ML model. Section 4 presents an analysis of the performance of different ML models within the classification and regression frameworks. Following this, Section 5 details the hybrid emulator setup, which emulates the proposed ML-based multi-connectivity solution. Section 6 evaluates the performance of the multi-connectivity solution for the target application requirements in both the regression and classification frameworks. Finally, Section 7 concludes the work and highlights the possible extensions for future research.

2. Related work

Multi-connectivity is increasingly being recognized as a crucial feature for increasing resilience and performance when single connectivity systems fail to meet the necessary application performance requirements. This technology may be essential for fulfilling the high throughput and ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) demands that define 5G and 6G networks. The study conducted by

Mishra et al. provides significant insights into the benefits of New Radio Dual Connectivity (NR-DC) [20]. Using the Simu5G network simulator, which is based on OMNeT++, the authors demonstrated that NR-DC can increase throughput by up to 14%, reduce latency by up to 33%, and improve reliability by up to 11% compared to single connectivity systems. These findings emphasize the potential of NR-DC in addressing the growing demands of 5G applications and enhancing the overall efficiency and reliability of modern wireless networks. Some studies have also explored intelligent network selection strategies for MC using both analytical models and learning-based approaches. Pirnagomedov et al. in [21] developed a mobility-oriented framework using queuing theory to allocate data rates in 5G networks. Their approach used reinforcement learning (RL) and transfer learning to minimize convergence time — the duration needed for the RL algorithms to stabilize their decision policies — enhancing UE throughput in dense millimeter-wave settings. In [22], Majamaa et al. proposed a dynamic packet duplication scheme for NTN connectivity, utilizing hybrid automatic repeat request feedback to improve network performance. The approach seeks to minimize redundant packet transmissions without compromising reliability. Additionally, deep learning has been explored in [23] to optimize traffic splitting in multi-connectivity scenarios, providing adaptive solutions for dynamic network conditions. In line with this, Lee et al. have proposed a RAT selection scheme with efficient MC configuration for uRLLC services [24]. By using distributed RL, devices can dynamically select appropriate RATs to enhance reliability and optimize resource usage, addressing the challenges of duplicate transmissions and traffic load.

Authors like Mahmood et al. have proposed a novel approach to improve the reliability and reduce latency of 5G URLLC services by transmitting the same data packet across multiple links [25]. This method demonstrates a latency reduction of up to 23% and a reliability improvement of up to 57% in system-level simulations. In addition, a mechanism is suggested to control user load, though its effectiveness and the average benefits are moderate and highly dependent on the system configuration. In a similar vein, Kucera et al. introduced a novel multi-connectivity framework that integrates 4G LTE, 5G, Wi-Fi, and WiGig wireless links to ensure reliable data delivery with controlled throughput and latency [26]. By employing software-defined transport-layer proxies, this framework enables deployment and upgrades without requiring modifications to networks. The authors evaluated the framework's effectiveness in managing user-centric bandwidth and latency for latency-sensitive applications through LTE and Wi-Fi network tests. This approach is suitable for supporting interactive cloud-based applications with stringent quality-of-service requirements.

The study conducted by Lübben and Schwardmann explored the potential of multi-connectivity options, such as multiple antennas and multi-path TCP, in real-world vehicular scenarios [27]. They observed that these methods could increase throughput, reduce delay, and improve reliability. They emphasized the challenges associated with multi-path TCP and demonstrated that adjusting the congestion control protocol could result in additional performance improvements. Further, Suer et al. investigated the effectiveness of two multi-connectivity scheduling strategies, packet duplication (PD) and load balancing (LB), to improve latency and reliability for latency-sensitive and throughput-sensitive applications over Wi-Fi and LTE networks [28]. The study found that PD effectively stabilized latency by reducing outliers, whereas LB was successful in reducing latency for nearly half of the packets in poor radio conditions. In addition, they explored packet splitting in industrial applications using private LTE and Wi-Fi 802.11ac networks [29]. The results indicated that, in low-load scenarios, packet duplication or packet splitting performed best, depending on the low and high link correlations. Under high-load conditions, load balancing resulted in the lowest latency and the highest reliability. The study emphasizes that network load significantly impacts the effectiveness of these schemes and suggests further research to develop dynamic multi-connectivity schedulers based on these insights. The authors

like Frink et al. presented a multi-connectivity solution for Wi-Fi that incorporates layer-4 (transport layer) scheduling mechanisms, such as packet duplication and best path scheduling, as well as a mobility coordinator scheme [30]. This approach aims to improve Wi-Fi performance in Industrial IoT scenarios by reducing latency to 30–80 ms with 99.9% reliability and mitigating handover delays, enabling seamless roaming in mobile conditions. The solution addresses the limitations of enterprise Wi-Fi for industrial applications, which typically suffer from high latency and reliability. The assessment demonstrated that both multi-connectivity approaches improved Wi-Fi efficiency in comparison to single-connectivity, resulting in a latency decrease of up to 46%, from 143 ms to 77–81 ms, even in the presence of concurrent network traffic.

Most of these studies employed multi-connectivity or analogous frameworks that primarily use static/predefined rule-based strategies to redirect or replicate packets across the available communication links. While a few studies have explored the use of ML for MC in different contexts, our approach advances this direction by incorporating an ML model that proactively predicts, in real-time from radio KPIs, when a communication link may fail to meet application requirements. This ensures seamless and reliable connectivity, which we demonstrate through a practical use case focused on livestock transportation monitoring in rural areas, thus bridging the gap between theoretical models and real-world deployment. For the ML model, we explore both classification and regression frameworks to ensure the broader applicability to applications that require continuous monitoring of network performance, as well as those with the need for categorization of network performance. The choice of the framework is driven by the specific requirements of the application. Consider situations in which the aim is to determine if network KPIs are above or below a set threshold; in such cases, a classification method is appropriate. However, when the objective is to predict the approximate values of network KPIs to guide future decisions, a regression approach is more suitable. The proposed ML model employs radio KPIs to forecast 5G link throughput and latency, enabling the optimal and efficient use of satellite links.

3. Data collection and KPIs analysis

The ML models in the proposed framework are trained and tested using datasets obtained from the measurement campaign conducted with both 5G and satellite connectivity [31]. During this campaign, various network KPIs were measured, including throughput and latency, as well as radio KPIs, specifically Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ) and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). We then used these data to train the ML models for both regression and classification, with radio KPIs serving as input features and network KPIs as outputs.

3.1. Measurement campaign

The measurement campaign was carried out in the northern part of Denmark, selected for its representative rural characteristics, including variable network coverage and infrastructure. The campaign involved evaluating both cellular networks and Starlink LEO satellite networks using commercially available modems. The measurements were conducted over several kilometers, encompassing diverse coverage conditions, which helps ensure that the findings are not limited to a single localized environment. For the cellular network, a SIMCOM SIM8202G-M2 5G modem was connected to a public 5G network, and the LEO satellite connectivity was achieved using a residential Starlink terminal in clear sky conditions. The two modems were mounted on a car driving at a low speed of 15 km/h to avoid the impact of high-speed mobility, which could otherwise complicate the analysis. It is important to note that clear-sky conditions may not fully reflect real-world scenarios, where environmental factors such as

rain and snow can affect signal quality and network performance. Recent studies indicate that rain can impact downlink (DL) performance, though the effect is generally very minimal [32]. Data collection was conducted at different times throughout the day and on various days of the week to capture the data under different network conditions. The *ping* and *iperf3* tests were performed to measure the round-trip time (RTT) and throughput, at a rate of ten and one measurement per second, respectively. Additionally, the RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR KPIs were gathered from the cellular modem at a rate of one measurement per second. These radio KPIs were chosen based on their practical availability from commercial 5G NSA modems and their established relevance to network performance. More detailed information about the measurement campaign can be found in [31].

Based on our cellular throughput and latency measurements, we observed instances where there was no clear correlation between network KPIs (i.e., latency and throughput) and radio KPIs (i.e., RSRP, RSRQ and SNR). This variability made it difficult to define static thresholds or simple rules that could reliably guide network selection - a limitation inherent to traditional reactive approaches. Our previous study provides a detailed explanation of this observation [13]. Acknowledging the complexities of this relationship, we adopted the ML-based proactive approach, which is capable of learning the underlying complex patterns and relationships between radio and network KPIs.

3.2. Analysis of KPIs

In this subsection, we discuss the preprocessing of the measurement data before feeding them to the ML model, as well as how we establish the threshold values for network KPIs specific to our use case.

3.2.1. Preprocessing of radio KPIs

To effectively extract the underlying trends from the measurement data, a moving average filter was implemented on the raw measurements. For throughput data, which was measured at an interval of one second, a window size of 60 s was used. This choice was made because it effectively smooths fluctuations while still reflecting meaningful changes in throughput patterns over time. Conversely, for latency data, which had ten measurements per second, a window size of 90 s was applied, as this window helped reduce the effects of short-term variations and offered a more comprehensive perspective on the overall latency performance. The selection of these averaging window sizes was based on preliminary analyses, which revealed the best balance between minimizing noise and identifying trends. This method also aligns with the throughput and latency measurements used in subsequent training and evaluation sessions for ML, where similar moving average filters were implemented: a sixty-second filter for throughput and a ninety-second filter for latency. Since throughput is measured at a higher protocol layer, independent of the radio KPIs, it is susceptible to fluctuations caused by buffering at lower levels of the network protocol stack, which can compromise its reliability for analysis. Similarly, latency measurements, which are taken at a finer granularity, are influenced by transient network conditions such as congestion, leading to potential variability that must be taken into account in the analysis.

3.2.2. Threshold for network KPIs

Based on the COMTECT requirements, we have established a throughput threshold of 25 Mbps for downlink transmission and 100 ms for latency. In order to proactively address potential connectivity issues, the throughput threshold is approximately 10 Mbps above the COMTECT requirement [14]. By doing so, we can address any challenges before they cause disruptions, ensuring smooth operation in livestock transport applications. We aim to analyze both the classification and regression frameworks for network throughput and latency. In the Regression framework, the ML models are used to predict the absolute values of throughput and latency. The decision to enable the satellite

Fig. 2. Overall framework for satellite/cellular multi-connectivity with classification/regression ML framework.

link is made based on whether these predicted values meet the predefined threshold levels. In the classification framework, we define binary classes for each network KPI:

- **Throughput Classification:**

- Class 0: Cases where throughput is less than the threshold of 25 Mbps.
- Class 1: Cases where throughput is greater than or equal to 25 Mbps.

- **Latency Classification:**

- Class 0: Cases where latency is less than the threshold of 100 ms.
- Class 1: Cases where latency is greater than or equal to 100 ms.

Detecting Class 0 in throughput and Class 1 in latency is more crucial, as these indicate situations where the cellular network is unable to provide the necessary service levels. Addressing these cases is crucial to ensure that the targeted application meets its performance requirements and operates reliably. Note that the decision is based on downlink throughput only, being far the most demanding of the two links; implicitly, we assume that the corresponding uplink throughput can be maintained given that the downlink requirement is met. The latency (RTT), on the other hand, covers both uplink and downlink.

4. ML framework and model selection

Fig. 2 illustrates an outline of the proposed framework for the efficient utilization of satellite links in multi-connectivity where 5G network serves as the primary source of connectivity to meet the latency and throughput requirements of the application. The satellite communication link serves as a backup, ensuring an uninterrupted connection in case the 5G network is unable to meet the application's requirements. To effectively switch between both networks, we utilize the ML model, with the classification or regression framework, that predicts network throughput and latency using radio KPIs as input. If the cellular link is activated and the model predictions reveal that the network performance is not in line with the application requirements, it suggests activating the backup satellite link and routes the packets to it. This approach ensures uninterrupted connectivity until the 5G network recovers.

4.1. Regression framework

For optimization in real-time, many applications require continuous monitoring of crucial performance indicators such as signal strength, latency, or throughput rather than identifying specific cases of these performance indicators. Regression models can be effective in these situations, offering accurate and dynamic predictions that are essential for improving overall network performance. In our regression framework, we explored three ML models: Random Forest (RF) [33], Decision Tree (DT) [34], and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) [35] for monitoring both throughput and latency. Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that constructs multiple decision trees during training

and outputs the average prediction of the individual trees, thereby reducing overfitting and capturing more complex patterns in the data. This approach often results in higher predictive accuracy compared to a single Decision Tree, especially for datasets with noise and non-linear relationships. A Decision Tree is a simple and interpretable model that splits data into subsets based on feature values, forming a tree-like structure. However, it tends to overfit the training data if not properly pruned, leading to poor generalization and lower R^2 scores. KNN is another non-parametric method that predicts target values based on the average of the nearest K data points in the feature space. It adapts well to the underlying data distribution without assuming a specific functional form, enhancing performance in various scenarios, though it can be computationally intensive and sensitive to noisy data. To assess the performance of the ML regression framework, the following metrics are used:

- **R2 Score:** This metric assesses how well the prediction of the models aligns with actual data. It represents the proportion of the dependent variable's variance that is predictable from the independent variables. A higher R2 Score, closer to 1, signifies a better fit, indicating that the model explains a significant portion of the outcome's variance.
- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** MSE measures the average squared difference between predicted values and actual values. It penalizes larger errors more than smaller ones, with lower MSE values reflecting better model performance, as they indicate smaller deviations from the true values.
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** MAE evaluates the average magnitude of errors in predictions without considering their direction. It provides a simple interpretation of prediction accuracy, with lower values indicating better performance.

4.2. Classification framework

Although sometimes regression and classification techniques can be applied to similar challenges, they serve different purposes. Particularly, classification models are effective for tasks that require clear-cut categorization. For instance, it can excel at assessing signal quality and assigning it to specific groups. This type of discrete output enables straightforward decision-making and allows for quick adjustments to changing network conditions. Whether to use regression or classification can be determined by the specific needs of the application, as each method provides distinct benefits to improve systems. In our multi-connectivity solution, for instance, classifying network link conditions can trigger the activation of a backup link (satellite) when the primary link (cellular) degrades, thereby ensuring a high level of QoS. In our previous research, we utilized an RF model that monitors radio KPIs and predicts cellular link throughput. However, in this paper, we are extending the previously utilized RF classification framework [13] to support the latency requirement of the targeted application. The following performance metrics are used to evaluate the RF classifier:

- **Precision:** It evaluates the accuracy of a model's predictions for a specific class by calculating the ratio of correctly identified instances to the total number of instances classified as that class. It indicates how reliable the model is in identifying members of the class under examination.
- **Recall:** It represents the fraction of correctly classified instances for the class of interest out of all actual instances in that class. It demonstrates how well the model can detect all relevant cases within the specified category.
- **f1-score:** It represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single metric that reflects the trade-off between these two performance indicators.

Table 1

Performance of the regression models on measured throughput and latency.

	Throughput			Latency		
	DT	KNN	RF	DT	KNN	RF
R2 Score	0.82	0.87	0.89	0.79	0.91	0.90
MSE	104.99	72.90	61.16	3477.92	1549.22	1643.14
MAE	3.90	4.25	4.21	14.71	12.67	16.07

Table 2

Classification performance for the RF model on measured throughput and latency.

	Latency			Throughput		
	Precision	Recall	f1-score	Precision	Recall	f1-score
Class 0	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.83	0.96	0.89
Class 1	0.95	0.90	0.92	1.00	0.99	0.99

4.3. Selection of ML model

For the regression framework, Table 1 compares the three ML models, DT, KNN, and RF, trained, tested, and evaluated over the measurement data, using R2 score, MSE, and MAE performance metrics for throughput and latency. Our evaluation of throughput measurement data showed that the R^2 score of the RF-trained model was similar to that of the KNN model and outperformed the DT model. This trend is attributed to RF's superior generalization and KNN's adaptability. The ensemble nature of RF handles noise and captures complex patterns, while KNN's flexibility prevents overfitting [36]. For latency prediction, the RF model achieves an R^2 score very close to that of the KNN model and outperforms the DT model. Although KNN shows lower MSE and MAE for latency, we select RF as it also delivers the best results for throughput prediction, with overall high R2 score, making it well-suited for both network KPIs. Using RF for both regression tasks simplifies the decision pipeline and aligns with our goal of developing a unified model for joint network KPIs prediction in future work, which would be more difficult with heterogeneous models. The study utilizes the RF Regressor with 100 trees, employing mean squared error as the criterion for split quality. This model allows for unrestricted tree growth, requires a minimum of two samples to split a node, and mandates that each leaf has at least one sample. All features are considered for finding splits, and bootstrap sampling is activated.

For the classification framework, the performance metrics for latency and throughput is shown in Table 2. Accurate prediction of Class 1 for latency is crucial because it indicates when the cellular link cannot meet the application's latency requirements, requiring the activation of the satellite link to prevent connection issues. Similarly, accurate prediction of Class 0 for throughput is critical as it indicates situations where the cellular link fails to meet the throughput requirements for livestock transport, resulting in the need for satellite activation to ensure seamless connectivity. As shown in Table 2, the model demonstrates good precision, recall, and f1-score for Class1 in the latency classification task and for Class 0 in the throughput classification task, with a high f1-score of approximately 0.9 in both cases. This supports the effectiveness of the classification framework in identifying these performance-sensitive cases.

5. Hybrid emulator setup

After having established the regression and classification frameworks for the proposed ML model, their performance was evaluated using the hybrid emulation setup shown in Fig. 3. The emulation setup consists of two Next Generation Units of Computing (NUC): one for emulating the cellular link (see Section 5.1) and the other for the satellite link (see Section 5.2). Specifically, NUC-2 was configured with the openSAND emulator to represent the satellite link, whereas NUC-1

Fig. 3. Hybrid emulator setup for evaluation of multi-connectivity solution.

was set up as the cellular emulator, and for executing the dynamic routing scheme with the trained ML model. The multi-connect tool (details in Section 5.3) was utilized in NUC-1 to direct the traffic to one of the communication links, either cellular or satellite. Together, the ML model and the multi-connect tool make up the dynamic routing scheme for the device side. It continuously monitors radio KPIs and uses the ML model to predict (wireless) network KPIs such as throughput and latency. Based on these predictions, and predefined application requirements, it selects the most appropriate link (cellular or satellite) and passes on the decision to the multi-connectivity tool that handles the actual routing and forwarding of packets over the selected interface. This integration ensures proactive, performance-aware, link selection and seamless traffic routing. On the network side, a server was employed with the multi-connectivity tool installed, receiving packets from the active link and processing them accordingly. The *iperf* and *ping* tools, mentioned in Section 3.1, were used at the device side to test the effectiveness of the dynamic routing scheme by measuring latency (RTT) and throughput, respectively.

5.1. Cellular emulator-traffic control network emulator

The traffic control network emulator (tc-netem) is a valuable tool within the framework of Linux traffic control (*tc*) that allows for realistic network emulation [18]. It can simulate a range of network impairments such as delays, data rates, packet loss, duplication, and corruption. We used tc-netem to emulate the behavior of the cellular link. This capability of tc-netem enabled us to evaluate the performance of the multi-connectivity solution under various network conditions without the need to deploy it in real environments at the initial stage. Specifically, empirical traces of cellular throughput and latency were replayed to preserve the temporal dynamics of real-world cellular

communication conditions. This approach enabled the approximation of the instantaneous packet rate, delay, and loss, thereby effectively replicating realistic network behavior [13]. Cellular throughput data were emulated at the same rate of one sample per second as used during the measurement campaign. This rate is a reasonable compromise between following the dynamics of the network conditions and the (kernel) timing limitations of tc-netem.

5.2. Satellite emulator-openSAND

The openSAND emulator is an open-source tool that enables researchers to replicate the DVB-RCS2 and DVB-S2 standards for satellite communication [17]. In our study, we employed the openSAND emulator to emulate the satellite link. The empirical latency traces collected from Starlink measurements were replayed within the openSAND emulator to preserve temporal characteristics and accurately replicate real-world satellite link behavior. The OpenSAND emulator was configured to ensure a minimum throughput of 25 Mbps on NUC-2 as per COMECT project requirements.

5.3. Multi-connect tool

To perform the multi-connectivity emulation, we utilized multi-connect, a software tool developed at Aalborg University [19]. The tool enables multi-connectivity by duplicating Transport Layer (Layer 4) UDP packets and transmitting them over either the satellite or cellular link. A Layer 3 tunnel is established over each of the duplication links, forming the foundation for multi-connectivity by encapsulating traffic and allowing seamless switching or duplication across interfaces. These tunnels also support performance evaluation using the Linux ping tool for latency measurements and iperf3 for throughput testing. The specific use of the tunnels, whether for redundancy (simultaneous

Table 3
Comparison of emulated performance for single and multi-connectivity approaches.

Network KPIs	Cellular		Dynamic Routing			
	Requirement Met (%)		Classification		Requirement Met (%)	Regression
		Class 0	Class 1		R2 score	Requirement Met (%)
Latency	71.8	97.8	89.7	81.7	0.9	83.7
Throughput	97.3	97.0	99.0	99.8	0.9	99.3

(a) Latency CCDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme.

(b) Latency CCDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme when SC latency exceeds 100 ms.

Fig. 4. Latency evaluation for the classification framework.

(a) Latency CCDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme.

(b) Latency CCDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme when SC latency exceeds 100 ms

Fig. 5. Latency CCDF for the regression framework.

transmission over both links) or optimized link selection, is governed by the routing scheme implemented within the application. ML-based MC introduces some computational overhead when compared to single connectivity due to the ML decision layer. The general complexity of the Random Forest (RF) model can be defined as $O(n \cdot d \cdot m \log(m))$ [37], where n is the number of samples, d is the number of features, and m represents the number of estimators (trees). In our case, the features are RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR, so $d = 3$, and the number of trees m is set to 100. Due to the linearithmic complexity, the model remains lightweight and efficient, making it suitable for deployment on typical devices. The hybrid MC emulator operates without the need for dedicated accelerators or high-end hardware. Its minimal computational footprint ensures that routing decisions are made in real-time, thereby facilitating uninterrupted transitions across both network interfaces.

6. Performance evaluation of multi-connectivity

In this section, we analyze the application performance using classification and regression frameworks for SC and MC (with dynamic routing). When analyzing latency, we focus on the Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF) as we are particularly interested in evaluating the performance of the dynamic routing scheme when the latency on the cellular link exceeds 100 ms. The CCDF enables us to assess the likelihood of latency surpassing this limit,

offering insights into how often and to what extent latency exceeds the acceptable level. Conversely, for throughput analysis, we use the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) as our focus is on assessing the performance of the dynamic routing scheme when the throughput on the cellular link goes below 25 Mbps. The CDF allows us to examine how often and to what degree throughput falls short of the desired performance benchmark.

In our results, we have considered three different cases for evaluating the overall performance:

- **Cellular Link:** SC over the cellular network.
- **Dynamic Routing:** MC based on the dynamic routing scheme, using either the classification or the regression framework.
- **Best Available Link:** The optimal performance is achieved by evaluating both cellular and satellite connections and selecting the best-performing link at any given moment. It serves as a benchmark against which to assess performance.

6.1. Latency analysis

The latency CCDF for the classification framework is shown in Fig. 4. It is observed from Fig. 4(a) that the cellular link (green color) shows a broader distribution of latencies as compared to the dynamic routing

(a) Throughput CDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme.

(b) Throughput CDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme when SC is less than 25 Mbps.

Fig. 6. Throughput evaluation with classification Framework.

scheme (blue color). Our primary interest lies in cases in which the cellular link latency exceeds 100 ms, cf. Fig. 4(b) where the results are conditioned on the cellular link latency exceeding 100 ms (note, the probability of the cellular link exceeding the threshold is 100% in Fig. 4(b)). It is observed that the dynamic routing scheme manages to reduce the latency, by effectively redirecting traffic to the satellite link when the cellular link experiences a latency greater than 100 ms. Additionally, it shows that the dynamic routing scheme gets close to the benchmark (red color).

The latency CCDF for the regression framework is illustrated in Fig. 5. In this framework, the ML model predicts absolute network latency based on radio KPIs, unlike the classification framework. If the ML regression model predicts latency greater than the threshold of 100 ms for the cellular link, dynamic routing will redirect packets to the satellite link to ensure the latency requirements of the application are met. To analyze the effectiveness of dynamic routing, Fig. 5(b) illustrates the CCDF when the cellular link experiences latency greater than 100 ms. We observe that dynamic routing successfully reroutes packets to the satellite link approximately 48% of the time using the ML model predictions, when the cellular link latency exceeds 100 ms. In this framework, dynamic routing aligns closer to the best available link latency compared to the classification framework. The regression framework provides a more precise prediction of the network latency, making the selection of the most optimal link more robust.

(a) Throughput CDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme.

(b) Throughput CDF for the SC and dynamic routing scheme when SC is less than 25 Mbps.

Fig. 7. Throughput evaluation with Regression Framework.

Table 4

Emulated latency (ms) statistics for SC (Cellular) and MC (Dynamic Routing) conditioned on the cellular link latency exceeding the threshold of 100 ms.

	Classification framework		Regression framework	
	SC	MC	SC	MC
Std.	146	73	146	64
Median	231	105	231	100
Mean	266	137	266	124
75%	333	157	333	123

By implementing ML-based dynamic routing, an improvement of approximately 10% is achieved in maintaining the network latency less than 100 ms compared to SC over cellular, cf. Table 3, Cellular 71.8% versus Dynamic Routing 81.7/83.7%; the dynamic routing scheme with regression achieves the biggest improvement of approximately 12%. Additionally, Table 4 compares the emulated latency statistics for SC and MC when the cellular link delays exceed the threshold of 100 ms. It can be seen that both classification and regression can reduce the latency by more than 125 ms in the mean in this case.

6.2. Throughput analysis

The throughput CDF for the classification framework is shown in Fig. 6. In this framework, the ML classifier model predicts the defined

Table 5

Emulated throughput (Mbps) statistics for SC and MC conditioned on the cellular link throughput being below 25 Mbps.

	Classification Framework		Regression Framework	
	SC	MC	SC	MC
Std	3	2	4	3
Median	18	30	19	30
Mean	18	30	19	28
75%	20	30	21	30

network throughput classes based on radio KPIs. The cellular SC link is able to provide at least 25 Mbps throughput 97.3% of the time, but Fig. 6(a) shows that the throughput distribution has a longer tail compared to dynamic routing, with a wider distribution of throughput values below 25 Mbps. Fig. 6(b) shows the distribution conditioned on the cellular link throughput being below 25 Mbps. Here, we observe that adopting the dynamic routing schemes significantly improves the probability of meeting the targeted throughput requirement, and improves the fulfillment of the throughput requirement by 2.6% compared to cellular SC, as shown in Table 3. Fig. 7 presents the throughput CDF using the regression framework, with the overall throughput CDF in Fig. 7(a) and the conditioned results (cellular throughput less than 25 Mbps) in Fig. 7(b). In this case, the dynamic routing scheme improves the fulfillment of the throughput requirement by 2.0% compared to cellular SC. Compared to the classification framework, we observe that the regression framework has more instances where the actual cellular throughput was below 25 Mbps, but the model predicted it to be greater than 25 Mbps. Table 5 shows the emulated throughput data for both SC and MC when the cellular link is below the threshold of 25 Mbps. It can be seen that both classification and regression can increase the throughput by approximately 10 Mbps in the mean in this case, with classification proving slightly more than regression. In both frameworks, the results show that the performance with dynamic routing, when optimally switching between interfaces, closely matches the “best available link” performance, as indicated by the statistical CDF behavior shown in Fig. 6(b) and Fig. 7(b).

Both throughput and latency evaluation validate that the MC framework consistently outperforms SC approaches under varying network conditions. This improvement is driven by the predictive switching logic of the ML-based system, which leverages real-time throughput and latency predictions derived from radio KPIs.

7. Conclusion

This paper proposed a multi-connectivity solution based on an ML-based dynamic routing scheme that enables the smart utilization of satellite and cellular links. The study evaluated the performance of the ML models, comprising two classifiers and two regressors, in identifying instances where the latency and throughput of the cellular links fail to meet the requirements for livestock transport monitoring. From training and evaluation with measured data, the RF regressor was chosen as the best for a joint throughput and latency regression framework; similarly, as an extension to previous work, also the RF model was found to be effective for both throughput and latency in the classification framework. Both frameworks use radio KPIs as input to identify when the cellular link cannot provide the necessary service and the satellite link needs to be activated. To emulate both communication links, a hybrid emulator was developed that utilized OpenSAND for satellite and tc-netem for cellular link emulation to evaluate the proposed framework. Our emulation results demonstrate that multi-connectivity significantly outperforms single cellular connectivity across both ML frameworks. Specifically, using the classification framework, fulfillment of throughput and latency requirements improved from 97.3% and 71.8% to 99.8% and 81.7%, respectively. Similarly, with the regression

framework, the throughput and latency requirement fulfillment improved from 97.3% and 71.8% to 99.3% and 83.7%, respectively. The threshold for the network KPIs presented in this study was determined for the livestock transport application. However, both ML frameworks can also be used for other applications that have limited 5G coverage, such as remote agriculture monitoring or autonomous vehicle operations in rural areas. In our use-case, to meet the latency requirement, we observed that the regression framework outperformed the classification framework. However, if the application focuses on meeting the throughput requirement, the classification framework performed slightly better than regression.

As future work, consistent measurements of packet throughput and latency could allow for the development of an integrated ML framework that simultaneously considers both throughput and latency for decision-making in the dynamic routing scheme. Also, to further validate the proposed solution, evaluation with measurements in other scenarios and weather conditions are needed.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Poonam Maurya: Writing – review & editing, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Alejandro Ramírez-Arroyo:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Troels Bundgaard Sørensen:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Sebastian Bro Damsgaard:** Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Poonam Maurya reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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